

ASSESSMENT OF GENETIC RESISTANCE TO ERWINIA AMYLOVORA IN LOCAL APPLE VARIETIES VIA QTL-LINKED MARKERS

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Abstract. Apple (*Malus domestica*) is a key fruit crop worldwide, but its cultivation is threatened by fire blight caused by *Erwinia amylovora*. In this study, molecular markers AE10-375, GE-8019, and CH-F7-Fb1 were used to assess genetic resistance to fire blight in 107 samples from local apple varieties in Uzbekistan. The AE10-375 marker was found in 81% of samples, CH-F7-Fb1_210 in 38.3%, and GE-8019 in 11.2%. Only 1.8% of genotypes carried all three resistance loci, indicating full resistance, while 39.2% were partially resistant. Allelic frequency analysis at the CH-F7-Fb1 locus showed a significant dominance of the non-resistant allele. These findings highlight the limited distribution of resistance genes among local varieties and underscore the importance of marker-assisted selection to enhance fire blight resistance in apple breeding programs.

Keywords: fire blight, apple, *Erwinia amylovora*, genetic resistance, molecular markers

Аннотация. Яблоня (*Malus domestica*) является одной из ключевых плодовых культур во всем мире, но ее выращиванию угрожает огневая болезнь, вызываемая *Erwinia amylovora*. В данном исследовании для оценки генетической устойчивости к огненной болезни у 107 образцов местных сортов яблони в Узбекистане использовались молекулярные маркеры AE10-375, GE-8019 и CH-F7-Fb1. Маркер AE10-375 был обнаружен в 81% образцов, CH-F7-Fb1_210 — в 38,3%, а GE-8019 — в 11,2%. Лишь 1,8% генотипов несли все три локуса устойчивости, что указывает на полную резистентность, тогда как 39,2% оказались частично устойчивыми. Анализ частоты аллелей в локусе CH-F7-Fb1 показал значительное доминирование нерезистентного аллеля. Эти результаты свидетельствуют об ограниченном распространении генов устойчивости среди местных сортов и подчеркивают важность маркер-ассистированного отбора для повышения устойчивости к огненной болезни в программах селекции яблони.

Ключевые Слова: огневая болезнь, яблоня, *Erwinia amylovora*, генетическая устойчивость, молекулярные маркеры

Annotatsiya. Olma (*Malus domestica*) dunyodagi asosiy mevali ekin biri bo'lib, yetishtirilishiga *Erwinia amylovora* keltirib chiqaradigan bakterial kuyish kasalligi tahdid solmoqda. Ushbu tadqiqotda O'zbekistondagi mahalliy olma navlaridan 107 ta namunaning bakterial kuyishga genetik chidamliligini baholash uchun AE10-375, GE-8019 va CH-F7-Fb1 molekulyar markerlaridan foydalanildi. AE10-375 markeri 81% namunalarda, CH-F7-Fb1_210 38,3% va GE-8019 11,2% namunalarda aniqlandi. Faqat 1,8% namunalar har uchala chidamlilik lokuslariga ega bo'lib, bu to'liq chidamlilikni, 39,2% namunalar esa qisman chidamlilikni ko'rsatdi. CH-F7-Fb1 lokusida allel chastotasini tahlil qilish chidamli bo'lmagan allelning sezilarli darajada ustunligini ko'rsatdi. Ushbu natijalar mahalliy navlar o'rtasida

chidamlilik genlarining cheklangan taqsimlanishini ta'kidlaydi va olma seleksiyasi dasturlarida bakterial kuyishga chidamlilikni oshirish uchun markerlarni tanlash muhimligini ko'rsatadi.

Kalit So'zlar: *Bakterial kuyish, olma, Erwinia amylovora, genetic chidamlilik, molekulyar markerlar.*

Introduction. Apple (*Malus domestica*) is one of the most widely cultivated fruits globally, making a significant contribution to the economy of many countries. However, numerous bacterial and fungal pathogens cause serious damage to the yield and fruit quality of this plant. One of these diseases is fire blight caused by *Erwinia amylovora* (1). The pathogen damages the flowers, fruits, branches, leaves, and generally all parts of the plant (2). The traditional method of combating fire blight is treatment with aminoglycoside antibiotics (3). However, the emergence of resistance to the applied antibiotics in pathogenic strains and other ecological factors reduce the effectiveness of this method (4).

Therefore, the propagation of disease-resistant apple varieties is considered a sustainable and environmentally effective approach. Resistance to fire blight has polygenic characteristics and is controlled by quantitative trait loci (QTL) (5). Research has identified fire blight resistance genes in wild apple species such as *M. fusca*, *M. baccata*, *M. prunifolia*, *M. ×atrosanguinea*, *M. ×robusta* var. *persicifolia*, *M. sieversii*, as well as in 'Evereste', *M. floribunda* 821, and *Malus ×robusta* 5 (6). For instance, the *FB_MR5* resistance locus identified in *Malus ×robusta* 5 is one of the most extensively studied genes (7). Another important QTL for fire blight resistance is *FB_F7*, identified in Fiesta's Linkage group 7 (8). Disease resistance loci are considered to have quantitative traits, and if a variety possesses only one resistance gene, pathogen strains can overcome this resistance. For example, *E. amylovora* strains with the *avrRpt2_EA* allele have been found to overcome the resistance of the *FB_MR5* gene (9). To address these challenges, modern breeding strategies are focusing on combining multiple resistance loci, utilizing marker-assisted selection (MAS), and leveraging biotechnological advancements (10). In this study, the presence of bacterial fire blight resistance genes in local apple varieties grown in Uzbekistan was analyzed using molecular genetic markers.

MATERIALS AND METHODS.

Plant Sample Collection and Genomic DNA Extraction

A total of 107 young leaf samples from about 70 local apple varieties were collected from the Republic of Karakalpakstan, Khorezm, and Surkhandarya regions. Before sampling, the signs of the disease were assessed by morphobiological observations, and the GPS coordinates of each sampling site were recorded. When isolating genomic DNA from leaf samples, the PureLink® Plant Total DNA Purification Kit (Thermo Fisher Scientific) kit was used, and the process was carried out according to the manufacturer's instructions. Quantitative and qualitative indicators of the isolated genomic DNA were assessed using the Nanophotometer NP80 (Implen) spectrophotometer.

Molecular Analysis

SCAR markers: AE10-375, GE-8019 and SSR marker: CH-F7-Fb1[11] were used to identify resistance loci to fire blight disease in local apple varieties of Uzbekistan (Table 1).

For Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR), lyophilized ready-to-use PCR-core kits (Isogen, Russia) were used. The reaction mixture for PCR-core with a volume of 20 µL contained; 20 ng of genomic DNA, 10 pM from each primer, 10 µl of standard buffer for PCR core. The amplification process was carried out on a Thermocycler VERITI amplifier (USA) using the following program: initial denaturation at 94°C for 4 minutes, followed by 35 cycles of: 94°C for

25 seconds, 56°C, 57°C and 58°C for 30 seconds (for GE-8019, CH-FB-F7, AE10-375 respectively), 72°C for 40 seconds, and a final elongation at 72°C for 4 minutes. The amplification products were separated by gel electrophoresis in a 2.5% agarose gel using 1xTBE buffer. DNA ladder markers (Thermo Fisher Scientific) of 100 bp length were used to assess the amplicon sizes.

Table 1

Primer sequence used in the study

Marker	Primer sequence	Amplicon size
AE10-375	F 5'-CTGAAGCGCACGTTCTCC-3' R 5'-CTGAAGCGCATCATTTCTGATAG-3'	375 bp
GE-8019	F 5'-TTGAGACCGATTTTCGTGTG-3' R 5'-TCTCTCCCAGAGCTTCATTGT-3'	397 bp
CH-F7-Fb1	F 5'-AGCCAGATCACATGTTTTTCATC-3' R 5'-ACAACGGCCACCAGTTTATC-3'	174 bp 210 bp

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

In this study, 107 apple tree samples were analyzed to assess genetic resistance to fire blight, focusing on three molecular markers: AE10-375, GE-8019, and CH-F7-Fb1. The CH-F7-Fb1 marker amplified two distinct fragments: a 174 bp fragment, commonly found but unrelated to resistance, and a 210 bp fragment associated with the FBF7 quantitative trait locus (QTL) conferring resistance. The AE10-375 and GE-8019 markers generated 375 bp and 397 bp fragments, respectively, in genotypes carrying the FBF7 QTL[11].

Among the studied samples, the AE10-375 marker was detected in 81% of cases, CH-F7-Fb1_210 in 38.3%, and GE-8019 in 11.2%. The non-resistant CH-F7-Fb1_174 allele was present in 71.9% of the samples. Furthermore, 14% of the accessions showed no amplification of any resistance-associated loci. The most frequent genetic combinations were the presence of AE10-375 alone (37.3% of samples) and the co-occurrence of AE10-375 and CH-F7-Fb1_210 (34.5%). A smaller proportion of samples carried both AE10-375 and GE-8019 (7.4%), while the combination of all three resistance loci was observed in only 1.9% of cases.

Genetic mapping data indicated that AE10-375 and GE-8019 are located on the same chromosome, approximately 10 centimorgans apart, flanking the FBF7 QTL region. Previous studies have reported that the simultaneous presence of these markers significantly enhances resistance to *Erwinia amylovora*[12] Similarly, the frequent co-detection of AE10-375 and CH-F7-Fb1_210 in the present study suggests close genetic linkage and reinforces their combined value in marker-assisted selection strategies.

Allelic frequency analysis at the CH-F7-Fb1 locus revealed a prevalence of the 174 bp allele (0.68) compared to the 210 bp allele (0.32), with a significant deviation from equal distribution ($\chi^2 = 34.38$; $p < 0.0001$). Regarding genotype composition, 55.1% of the samples were homozygous for the 174 bp allele, 21.5% were homozygous for the 210 bp allele, and 16.8% were heterozygous, while 6.5% of the samples remained undetermined. Due to the dominant nature of AE10-375 and GE-8019, homozygous and heterozygous states could not be distinguished, and their presence was scored as 2. In contrast, the codominant CH-F7-Fb1 marker allowed differentiation between homozygous and heterozygous genotypes. Homozygotes for CH-F7-Fb1_210 were assigned an index value of 2, whereas heterozygotes (210/174) were assigned -1, considering the presence of the non-resistant 174 allele.

The calculated resistance indices across samples ranged from 0 to 6. Based on the combination of loci, genotypes were classified as unstable (rr, carrying none or only one marker), partially resistant (Rr, carrying two markers), or fully resistant (RR, carrying all three markers). According to this classification, 58.8% of the genotypes were non-resistant, 39.2% were partially resistant, and only 1.8% were fully resistant. Allele frequencies for r and R were estimated at 0.78 and 0.21, respectively, fitting Hardy–Weinberg expectations ($\chi^2 = 2.84$; $p = 0.091$).

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REFERENCES.

1. Zhao, Y.Q., TIAN, Y.L., WANG, L.M., GENG, G.M., ZHAO, W.J., HU, B.S. and Zhao, Y.F., 2019. Fire blight disease, a fast-approaching threat to apple and pear production in China. *Journal of Integrative Agriculture*, 18(4), pp.815-820.
2. Van Der Zwet, T. and Beer, S.V., 1999. Fire blight--its nature, prevention, and control: a practical guide to integrated disease management.
3. Wallis, A.E. and Cox, K.D., 2020. Management of fire blight using pre-bloom application of prohexadione-calcium. *Plant disease*, 104(4), pp.1048-1054.
4. McManus, P.S., Stockwell, V.O., Sundin, G.W. and Jones, A.L., 2002. Antibiotic use in plant agriculture. *Annual review of phytopathology*, 40(2002), pp.443-465.
5. Peil, A., Bus, V.G., Geider, K., Richter, K., Flachowsky, H. and Hanke, M.V., 2009. Improvement of fire blight resistance in apple and pear. *Int J Plant Breed*, 3(1), pp.1-27.
6. Kost, T.D., Gessler, C., Jansch, M., Flachowsky, H., Patocchi, A. and Broggini, G.A., 2015. Development of the first cisgenic apple with increased resistance to fire blight. *PLoS One*, 10(12), p.e0143980.
7. Peil, A., Garcia-Libreros, T., Richter, K., Trognitz, F.C., Trognitz, B., Hanke, M.V. and Flachowsky, H., 2007. Strong evidence for a fire blight resistance gene of *Malus robusta* located on linkage group 3. *Plant Breeding*, 126(5), pp.470-475.
8. Khan, M.A., Duffy, B., Gessler, C. and Patocchi, A., 2006. QTL mapping of fire blight resistance in apple. *Molecular Breeding*, 17, pp.299-306.
9. Vogt, I., Wöhner, T., Richter, K., Flachowsky, H., Sundin, G.W., Wensing, A., Savory, E.A., Geider, K., Day, B., Hanke, M.V. and Peil, A., 2013. Gene-for-gene relationship in the host–pathogen system *Malus × robusta* 5–*E. amylovora*. *New Phytologist*, 197(4), pp.1262-1275.
10. Peil, A., Richter, K., Wensing, A., Höfer, M., Emeriewen, O.F. and Wöhner, T., 2021, March. Fire blight resistance breeding. In *IV International Symposium on Horticulture in Europe-SHE2021* 1327 (pp. 65-72).
11. Лыжин, А.С. and Савельева, Н.Н., 2021. МОЛЕКУЛЯРНО-ГЕНЕТИЧЕСКИЙ АНАЛИЗ СОРТОВ ЯБЛОНИ ПО QTL FBF7 УСТОЙЧИВОСТИ К БАКТЕРИАЛЬНОМУ ОЖОГУ. *Научные труды Северо-Кавказского федерального научного центра садоводства, виноградарства, виноделия*, 33, pp.97-100.
12. Khan, M.A., Durel, C.E., Duffy, B., Drouet, D., Kellerhals, M., Gessler, C. and Patocchi, A., 2007. Development of molecular markers linked to the ‘Fiesta’ linkage group 7 major QTL for fire blight resistance and their application for marker-assisted selection. *Genome*, 50(6), pp.568-577.